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THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSMENT AND CORRECTION OF MOVEMENT
ASYMMETRIES IN SPORTSMEN

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Abstract. This article discusses the methods of assessment and correction of movement asymmetries in athletes during training and rehabilitation. In both cases, the methods for the assessment of movement asymmetries include dynamometers, simple exercises with dumbbells, force plates, treadmills, and other techniques, motion analysis methods, and combined methods with the use of EMG, EEG, and other techniques for investigation of the sportsman's physiological and psychological condition. For each athlete, it is recommended to obtain the normal range of asymmetry and control it over time. Three types of movement asymmetry should be controlled: muscle strength asymmetry, joints' ranges (ROM) asymmetry, and reaction asymmetry. The following factors should be taken into account: the sportsman's genetics, his psychological and physiological condition, nutrition plan, and history of previous injuries. The effectiveness of exercises during training or rehabilitation may be increased by changing musculoskeletal strains to achieve optimal conditions for each tissue under consideration.

Keywords: Movement asymmetry, sport, rehabilitation, mechanobiology, motion analysis, FMS.

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აბსტრაქტი. ამ სტატიაში განხილულია სპორტსმენებში საწვრთნო პროცესის და რეაბილიტაციის დროს მოძრაობების ასიმეტრიის შეფასებისა და კორექტირების მეთოდები. ორივე შემთხვევაში მოძრაობის ასიმეტრიის შეფასების მეთოდები მოიცავს დინამომეტრებს, მარტივ ვარჯიშებს ჰანტელების, ძალის პლატფორმების, სარბენი ბილიკების და სხვა ტექნიკის გამოყენებით, მოძრაობის ანალიზის მეთოდებს, და კომბინირებულ მეთოდებს EMG, EEG გამოყენებით და სპორტსმენის ფიზიოლოგიური და ფსიქოლოგიური მდგომარეობის გამოკვლევის სხვა მეთოდებს. თითოეული სპორტსმენისთვის რეკომენდებულია ასიმეტრიის ნორმალური დიაპაზონის განსაზღვრა და დროთა განმავლობაში მისი კონტროლი. მოძრაობების ასიმეტრიის სამი ტიპი უნდა კონტროლდებოდეს: კუნთების სიძლიერის ასიმეტრია, სახსრების დიაპაზონის (ROM) ასიმეტრია და რეაქციის ასიმეტრია. გასათვალისწინებელია შემდეგი ფაქტორები: სპორტსმენის გენეტიკა, მისი ფსიქოლოგიური და ფიზიოლოგიური მდგომარეობა, კვების გეგმა და წინა ტრავმების ისტორია. ვარჯიშის ან რეაბილიტაციის დროს სავარჯიშოების ეფექტიანობა შეიძლება გაიზარდოს ძვალ-კუნთოვანი დატვირთვის რეგულირებით, რათა მივაღწიოთ ოპტიმალურ პირობებს თითოეული ქსოვილისთვის.

საკვანძო სიტყვები: მოძრაობის ასიმეტრია, სპორტი, რეაბილიტაცია, მექანობიოლოგია, მოძრაობის ანალიზი, FMS.

Introduction. In our recent articles, we discussed the molecular origin of movement asymmetries and methods of their analysis in athletes [1, 2]. It was shown that movement asymmetries are relatively normal in sports and they should be treated individually. Movement asymmetries assessment and measurement methods were also discussed in detail [2]. However little has been said about the different types of movement asymmetries and methods for assessing and correcting them. Their mechanobiological aspects were also not considered.

In this paper, we discuss different types of asymmetry from the mechanobiological point of view and suggest methods for their assessment and correction in sportsmen during training and rehabilitation.

Objectives. The main purpose of our article is to create a unified methodology for assessing and correcting different types of movement asymmetry among athletes during training and

rehabilitation. Another goal of this research is the use of a mechanobiological approach describing the process of training and exercising.

Materials and methods. We explored the recent scientific literature relating to themes reported in the Objectives section, as well as the keywords ‘movement asymmetry; sports; physical rehabilitation; mechanobiology; motion analysis; genetics; nutrition’. For this purpose, we used scientific search engines such as PubMed and Google Scholar. In our search, we excluded retracted publications and non-English articles.

Discussion. Movement asymmetries may be treated mechanobiologically: mechanical signals play a pivotal role in the formation of structurally and functionally appropriate body templates through cellular and tissue remodeling. Mechanobiology is a new multidisciplinary field that studies how cells sense and respond to mechanical signals [3]. Many biological activities may be regulated by mechanical forces.

The body responds to mechanical stimuli engendered through physical movement in an integrated fashion, internalizing and transferring forces from organ, through tissue and cellular length scales [3].

Physical exercises involve both anabolic and catabolic processes: anabolic processes are responsible for repairing muscle tissues after exercise, while catabolic processes are responsible for breaking down sugars to provide ATP to do the work necessary for exercise, such as muscle contractions [4].

Figure 1. The effect of tissue strain on the condition of the tissue [4].

It, therefore, follows that each tissue must have an optimal mechanical stimulus or “sweet spot” that maximizes anabolic tissue adaptation, where loads are neither too high to cause tissue damage, nor too low to result in tissue degeneration.

Figure 2 shows how a performance level in sports may be affected by increased or decreased training load or reduced recovery [5].

According to the modern approaches to training and rehabilitation, there are three main types of movement asymmetries:

1. Strength asymmetry;
2. Joints’ ranges of motion (ROM) asymmetry;
3. Reaction asymmetry.

Figure 2. Dependence of the quality of sports performance on the load, recovery time, and correctness of training [5].

Each of them requires measurements and assessment methods: strength measurements can be carried out using dynamometers and force platforms, joints' ranges of motion (ROM) measurements – using goniometry and motion analysis methods [6, 7, 8], and reaction time measurements – with the help of special devices and computers [9]. To improve strength asymmetry, we can use more symmetrical strength exercises, to improve ROMs' asymmetry – more flexibility exercises, especially for less flexible joints, and to improve reaction asymmetry we recommend special exercises and cognitive tests [10].

As there is no generally accepted method for estimation of the athlete's movement asymmetries coefficient, coaches and physical medicine specialists use some standard exercises and measurements to assess athletes' movement asymmetries, for example, they use left and right-hand force measurements, single-hand exercises with balls and dumbbells to assess the upper limbs movements asymmetry, vertical jumps on a single leg to assess the lower limbs movement asymmetry, and ROMs' measurements of active joints to assess flexibility asymmetry. By comparing the obtained results to the normal parameters for these exercises, coaches and physical medicine specialists can detect deviations of the athletes' movement asymmetries from the normal values and take proper measures.

Results. Regarding the acceptable thresholds of asymmetry, scientists agree that 10–15% asymmetry between limbs is not normal [11, 12], while less than 10% asymmetry has been suggested as a goal for athletes returning to sport after rehabilitation [12]. At the same time, experts agree that movement asymmetries should be treated individually, taking into account the athlete's genetic, physiological, and physical data. Therefore, it is necessary to determine and control the optimal percentage of the athlete's movement asymmetries.

For this purpose, scientists successfully use inertial sensors: IMU Step inertial sensors allow us to measure the load on the athlete's lower limbs during exercise and control movement asymmetries through mobile and desktop apps [13]. If the difference between the normal and observable asymmetries is too large (more than 5%), then something should be done to normalize the level of movement asymmetry [13].

The research results are shown in Figures 1, 2. Figures 1 and 2 demonstrate how the assessment and correction of movement asymmetries may be integrated into the training process and rehabilitation.

Figure 1. The integration of movement asymmetry assessment and correction modules into the training process.

Figure 2. The integration of movement asymmetry assessment and correction modules into the rehabilitation process.

Conclusion. Movement asymmetries in sports should be treated seriously, because they may lead to poor performance and injuries. Movement asymmetries are usually caused by increasing training load or reduced recovery, old injuries, bad nutrition plans, genetic predisposition to injury, and physical or psychological problems. They manifest themselves through low athletic performance, a decline in the growth curve of sports results, and fatigue. They can be detected using special tests that include physical exercises and measurements for assessment of different types of movement asymmetry: strength asymmetry, joints' ranges of motion (ROM) asymmetry, and reaction asymmetry. It is recommended for each athlete to obtain the optimal ranges of movement asymmetries for these types of asymmetry and control them over time. During training, we should regulate musculoskeletal loads to avoid overtraining or undertraining, while during rehabilitation we can use in addition mechanotherapy methods such as vibration platforms, interventional ultrasound, and massage. The mechanobiological approach may help us understand the overall effect of physical forces on tissue homeostasis and find optimal strategies for conducting training and rehabilitation sessions, taking into account the specific characteristics of a particular sport, the qualification, and the physical condition of the athlete.

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